

CAUSES OF IRON DEFICIENCY DURING PREGNANCY AND ITS PREVENTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13386958>

Abstract. *Iron deficiency anemia (WAIT) is the most common disease among women of childbearing age. According to WHO, children and expectant mothers are more susceptible to anemia. Iron is a trace element that is part of the vital protein-hemoglobin. It is an integral part of red blood cells — red blood cells that are responsible for transporting oxygen and removing carbon dioxide.*

Keywords: *iron, pregnancy, trace element, blood, hemoglobin.*

The aim of the study. Iron is the mediator of oxygen retention in the body, which delivers it to all organs and tissues and ensures their adequate functioning. Deficiency of this trace element leads to a decrease in hemoglobin and impaired transport function of erythrocytes. As a result, "oxygen starvation" occurs at the cellular level. This condition is called iron deficiency anemia.

Research materials and methods.

Iron deficiency in pregnant mothers occurs due to a combination of general and pregnancy-related factors. Reasons related to pregnancy: increased need for iron. Microelements are actively used for the growth of the fetus and the increase in the number of red blood cells of the mother. In the 2nd trimester, the placenta is formed, which together with the baby forms a single fetoplacental system. From this moment, the increase in iron consumption is spent on the adequate functioning of this complex. This condition is characterized by an uneven increase in the volume of circulating blood and the number of red blood cells. The rate of creation of red blood cells does not correspond to the rate of increase in blood volume, which leads to the development of anemia. When examining pregnant women from different regions, iron deficiency anemia was found in most of them.

100 pregnant women were taken for examination, 70 of them had Fe, Zh, Cu, B12, ferritin, and the remaining 30 had Fe, ferritin, B12 blood analysis. In the analysis, the amount of Fe in 25 pregnant women was 5.7, Zh-4.9, Cu-27.5, B12-93.6, and ferritin was 72.66. In 35 of them, the amount of Fe was 21.2, Zh-4.5, Cu-15.6, B12-293.0, and ferritin was 52.4. In the remaining 40, Fe content was 20.4, B12-213.0, and ferritin was 87.5. A comprehensive examination of 100 pregnant women was conducted. Pregnant women under the age of 20 and between the ages of 20 and 35 were observed in the study. Pregnant women of 20-38 weeks were observed. Women's anamnestic data, pregnancy, childbirth, postpartum period and neonatal period were analyzed. Pregnant women with iron deficiency anemia were divided into the following groups. 5% are under the age of 20, 50% belong to 21-25 years, 30% - to 26-30 years, 15% - to 31-35 years. The total number of pregnant women checked according to birth parity: those who were pregnant for the first time - 45% (52), women who were pregnant again - 55% (48). Discussion of the research results: The amount of blood lost in pregnant women with mild anemia during childbirth was 300-400 ml. In pregnant women with severe anemia, it was 600-700 ml. It was found that women with severe anemia had a difficult childbirth process (Slowness of labor, pathological bleeding).

The obtained results. During the general blood analysis of pregnant women under observation, 68% had a mild level of iron deficiency anemia, 20% had a moderate level of iron deficiency anemia, and 12% had a severe level of iron deficiency anemia. Early toxicosis was observed in 30% of physiologically pregnant women, and in the remaining 70%, the pregnancy was normal. 10% of pregnant women observed dizziness, 25% - nausea, 15% - freezing of hands and feet, 10% - pale skin, 40% had no symptoms.

There are two large groups of symptoms of anemia - hypoxic syndrome and sideropenic syndrome. The diversity of clinical symptoms is related to the fact that iron enters into the composition of a large number of enzymes and controls their operation. Its deficiency leads to a discrepancy in metabolic processes and, as a result, metabolic diseases. If iron deficiency anemia is found during pregnancy, it can have negative consequences for both the mother's body and the fetus. The possibility of complications depends on the severity and duration of the disease.

Currently, iron deficiency anemia is the basis of pathological changes that occur during pregnancy. This indicator is 40-50% and has increased 6, 8 times in the last 10 years (1, 4, 7). According to world medical statistics, the prevalence of anemia during pregnancy in developing countries is 35-56% in Africa, 37-75% in Asia and 37-52% in Latin America. A common etiological factor of this disease is assumed to be a deficiency of iron and folic acid. 20% of pregnant women's hemoglobin level does not exceed 80 g/l, 2-7% of patients have a hemoglobin level of 70 g/l.

Pathological complications that occur during childbirth cause deep changes in pregnant women, disrupt the adaptation process in the body, and cause post-partum complications in the body of the fetus and pregnant woman by providing disadaptation. The reason for the late diagnosis of postpartum anemia is that mothers pay more attention to the child without paying attention to their own health, especially young mothers.

Discussion of research results. The diagnosis of iron deficiency anemia is based on visual examination, instrumental examination of the patient, and evaluation of the results of laboratory blood analysis. Along with the study of patient's history and physical examination, attention is paid to the condition of the skin, the mucous membrane of the mouth, the corners of the lips, and the size of spleen is estimated by palpation.

The diagnosis of TTA is not limited to the detection of iron deficiency. For the correct treatment of this condition, the specialist prescribes auxiliary instrumental analyzes in order to clarify the pathogenesis of the disease. In mild and moderate anemia, oral medications are prescribed, and extensive scientific research in recent years has shown that bivalent and trivalent iron preparations are equally effective. Such regimens have proven to be more effective than high-dose treatment with repeated intake throughout the day and have a lower rate of side effects. When we gave pregnant women with moderate anemia for 3 months, we found that they had a much better effect. We prescribed Fercinol t/i to some pregnant women because they had very low analysis results.

Conclusions: WHO experts recommend the treatment of iron deficiency anemia in pregnant women with supplementation with folic acid and ascorbic acid for better iron absorption. Anti-anemia therapy is aimed at eliminating the symptoms of oxygen starvation, stabilizing hemodynamic parameters and normalizing metabolic processes. A specific diet rich in iron-containing foods is considered as a preventive measure, waiting and increasing the effectiveness of drugs. Many people think that the level of hemoglobin in the blood can be adjusted only by

normalizing the diet and including foods rich in iron, vitamin B12 or folic acid. Self-treatment is unacceptable and can lead to the development of a number of complications. With such schemes, the frequency of side effects is significantly reduced compared to taking high doses several times a day. For better assimilation of iron preparations, patients are prescribed ascorbic acid and folic acid. In addition, it is recommended to follow a special diet based on iron-rich foods.

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